

Supporting information: Thermoelectric enhancement in single organic radical molecules

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I) Theory

1. Orbital Analysis

In order to predict destructive quantum interference (DQI) and constructive QI (CQI) in molecules, one can use their molecular orbitals (wavefunctions). Consider the wavefunction for energy level E_n at site i is $\psi_n(i)$, the QI is expected to be destructive at the middle of the HOMO-LUMO gap $E_{HL} = (E_L + E_H)/2$ if

$$\frac{\psi_H(i)\psi_H^*(j)}{E_{HL} - E_H} + \frac{\psi_L(i)\psi_L^*(j)}{E_{HL} - E_L} = 0 \quad (1)$$

where ψ_H and ψ_L are HOMO and LUMO wave functions, respectively. Since $E_{HL} - E_H > 0$ and $E_{HL} - E_L < 0$, equation (1) will only be satisfied if the sign of $\psi_H(i)\psi_H^*(j)$ was the same as the sign of $\psi_L(i)\psi_L^*(j)$. Figure S1 shows the wavefunctions of Blatter radical molecular cores calculated using DFT and a simple one orbital per atom tight-binding (TB) model. In this figure, the size and colour of the circles represent the sign and amplitude of the wavefunction at a given site, respectively.

Figure S1. DFT and TB molecular orbitals. **a.** To construct TB Hamiltonian for TB orbital calculations, one orbital per atom is used with on-site energies 0 and -1.2 for carbon and nitrogen, respectively, and hopping integrals to the nearest neighbour of -1. **b.** Orbital analysis for Blatter radical cores using a simple TB model. In the *para*-connected core, DQI is predicted for spin-up (majority spin) electrons, whereas CQI is predicted for minority spins (spin-down). In the *meta*-connected cores, CQI is predicted for spin-up (majority spin) electrons whereas DQI is predicted for minority spins (spin-down).

From DFT wavefunction calculations, it is clear that the HOMO orbital for spin-up (majority spin) electrons is similar to the LUMO of spin-down (minority spin) electrons. Also, the LUMO orbital for spin-up electrons is similar to LUMO+1 of spin-down electrons. In other words, the molecular orbitals for spin-up and -down electrons seem similar, the only difference is that the Fermi energy is moved one level down (Figure S1). This

implies that a simple orbital rule analysis can be used even at the TB level to predict QI in magnetic molecules.

Figure S2. Molecular orbitals of radicals. The iso-surfaces of the molecular orbitals of radical molecules **1** (a) and **2** (b).

2. Spin dependent transmission functions

Using molecular orbital analysis, DQI is expected for spin-up electrons with the *para*-connected radical core because the sign of the product of wavefunction amplitudes at connection sites is negative (Figure S1). In contrast, CQI is expected for spin-down electrons with connectivities (Figure S1). This is in agreement with DFT transmission calculations for spin-up and -down electrons (Figure S3). In this Figure, there is an anti-resonance between the HOMO and the LUMO of spin-up electrons (blue curve in Figure S3a) whereas QI is constructive for spin-down electrons (red curve in Figure S3a). The behaviour of the *meta*-connected radical core is opposite where CQI (DQI) is expected for spin-up (-down) electrons.

Figure S3. Spin dependent transmission coefficients. Spin-up (blue), spin-down (red) and total (dashed black) transmission coefficient for molecules **1-3** and **1a**. **a. 1, b. 2, c. 3 and d. 1a.**

Figure S4. Total transmission coefficients for molecule 1-3 and closed shell analogue of 1 and 2 radicals. a. Transmission coefficient, **b.** electrical conductance and **c.** Seebeck coefficient at $E_F=0$. Molecules 4 and 5 are closed shell analogue of molecule 1 and 2 respectively where a hydrogen atom is connected to the nitrogen atom in the central ring.

3. Conformation dependent properties

Figure S5. The effect of anchor electrode conformations on transmissions. Transmission coefficient through radical molecule 1 and 2 with three different connection conformations to electrodes. **a.** molecular structure of junctions, **b.** Transmission coefficient and, **c.** Seebeck coefficient at DFT Fermi energy. This figure demonstrates the origin of high conductance group in our experiment.

Figure S6. Transmission coefficient through π -stacked dimer molecules formed by molecule 2. **a.** molecular structure of junctions with two different conformations (*I*, *II*) of π -stacked dimer and, **b.** corresponding transmission coefficients. This figure demonstrates a possible origin of the low conductance group in our experiments.

Figure S7. The molecular length for *para*- and *meta*- connected radicals.

4. Computational methods

Geometry optimization: The geometry of each structure studied in this paper was relaxed to the force tolerance of $10 \text{ meV}/\text{\AA}$ using the SIESTA¹ implementation of density functional theory (DFT), with a double- ζ polarized basis set (DZP) and the Local Density Approximation (LDA) functional with CA parameterization. A real-space grid was defined with an equivalent energy cut-off of 250 Ry. To calculate molecular orbitals and spin density of gas phase molecules, an experimentally parameterised B3LYP functional was employed using Gaussian g09v2² with 6-311++g basis set and tight convergence criteria.

Electron transport: To calculate the electronic properties of the device, from the converged DFT calculation, the underlying mean-field Hamiltonian H was combined with our quantum transport code, GOLLUM^{3,4}. This yields the transmission coefficient $T_e(E)$ for electrons of energy E (passing from the source to the drain) via the

relation $T_e(E) = \text{Tr}(\Gamma_L^e(E)G_e^R(E)\Gamma_R^e(E)G_e^{R\dagger}(E))$ where $\Gamma_{L,R}^e(E) = i(\Sigma_{L,R}^e(E) - \Sigma_{L,R}^{e\dagger}(E))$ describes the level broadening due to the coupling between left L and right R electrodes and the central scattering region, $\Sigma_{L,R}^e(E)$ are the retarded self-energies associated with this coupling, and $G_e^R = (ES - H - \Sigma_L^e - \Sigma_R^e)^{-1}$ is the retarded Green's function, where H is the Hamiltonian and S is the overlap matrix obtained from SIESTA implementation of DFT. DFT+ Σ approach has been employed for spectral adjustment³.

Thermoelectric properties: Using the approach explained in^{3,5}, the electrical conductance $G = G_0L_0$ and the Seebeck coefficient $S = -L_1/eTL_0$ are calculated from the electron transmission coefficient $T_e(E)$ where the momentums $L_n = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dE (E - E_F)^n T_e(E)(-\partial f_{FD}(E, T, E_F)/\partial E)$ and f_{FD} is the Fermi-Dirac probability distribution function $f_{FD} = (e^{(E-E_F)/k_B T} + 1)^{-1}$, T is the temperature, E_F is the Fermi energy, $G_0 = 2e^2/h$ is the conductance quantum, e is electron charge and h is the Planck's constant.

II) Experiment

1. Synthesis

Instrumentation. NMR spectra were recorded in deuterated solvent solutions on a Varian VNMRS-600 spectrometer and referenced against solvent resonances (^1H , ^{13}C) using compressive sampling for all unstable compounds⁶⁻⁸. ^{19}F NMR spectra were recorded in deuterated solvents on a Bruker Avance III-HD-400 spectrometer. ASAP data were recorded on a Xevo QTOF (Waters) high resolution, accurate mass tandem mass spectrometer equipped with Atmospheric Pressure Gas Chromatography (APGC) and Atmospheric Solids Analysis Probe (ASAP). Microanalyses were performed by Elemental Analysis Service, London Metropolitan University, UK or Elemental Microanalysis service, Durham University, UK.

General details. The compounds 4-iodo-*N*-(4-iodophenyl)benzimidoyl chloride, 4-iodo-*N*-phenylbenzimidoyl chloride, 4-iodo-*N*-(4-methoxyphenyl)benzimidoyl chloride, and 7-(trifluoromethyl)-1,3-bis(4-iodophenyl)-1,4-dihydrobenzo-[1,2,4]triazin-4-yl were prepared according to published methods⁹. All other chemicals were sourced from standard chemical suppliers.

Diarylbzimidohydrazide for pseudo-*para* isomers: general procedure

Arylhydrazine hydrochloride (1 eq) was slowly added to a solution containing 4-iodo-*N*-(4-iodophenyl)benzimidoyl chloride (1 eq) and anhydrous triethylamine (2 eq) in anhydrous dichloromethane (30 mL) at 0 °C. The solution was allowed to warm to room temperature over a period of 16 hours, and was then washed with 0.1 M HCl, collecting the organic layer. This was dried over MgSO_4 and filtered. Hexane was added to the filtrate until a 3:1 DCM:Hexane solution was achieved, and the solution was passed through a 10

cm long silica plug under pressure. The pale-yellow band was then collected and the solvent removed. Hexane was added to the residue and sonicated, forming a pale-yellow precipitate, which was collected by filtration and dried under vacuum. Note: Once isolated, diarylylbenzimidohydrazide was unstable in solution after 1 hour, and would slowly decay in the solid-state unless the sample was maintained in a dry, inert atmosphere.

4-iodo-N'-(4-iodophenyl)-N''-phenylbenzimidohydrazide. **Yield:** 2.82 g (49%). **¹H NMR** (600 MHz; CD₂Cl₂): δ_H 7.73 (br, 1H, H_f), 7.70 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.5 Hz, 2H, H_b), 7.50 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.8 Hz, 2H, H_d), 7.44 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.6 Hz, H_a), 7.26 (dd, ³J_{HH} = 8.6 Hz, ³J_{HH} = 7.3 Hz, 2H, H_h), 7.11 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.6 Hz, 2H, H_g), 6.88 (t, ³J_{HH} = 7.3 Hz, 1H, H_i), 6.48 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.8 Hz, 2H, H_c), 5.59 (br, 1H, H_e) ppm. **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (150 MHz; CD₂Cl₂): δ_C 145.0, 141.8, 138.5, 138.0, 135.6, 134.6, 129.6, 128.3, 120.9, 118.3, 113.6, 94.8, 82.7 ppm. **Acc-MS(ASAP⁺):** *m/z* 539.9437 [M+H]⁺ calcd. for C₁₉H₁₆N₃O₂ *m/z* 539.9434 (|Δ*m/z*| = 0.6 ppm). **Anal. Calc.** for C₁₉H₁₅I₂N₃: C, 42.33; H, 2.80; N, 7.79 %. **Found:** C, 42.16; H, 2.74; N, 7.70 %.

4-iodo-N'-(4-iodophenyl)-N''-(4-methoxyphenyl)benzimidohydrazide. **Yield:** 1.33 g (22%). **¹H NMR** (600 MHz; CD₂Cl₂): δ_H 9.60 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.2 Hz, 2H, H_a), 7.60 (s, 1H, H_f), 7.49 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.6 Hz, 2H, H_d), 7.42 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.3 Hz, 2H, H_b), 7.06 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.8 Hz, 2H, H_g), 6.84 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.4 Hz, 2H, H_h), 6.47 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.7 Hz, 2H, H_c), 5.59 (s, 1H, H_e), 3.76 (s, 3H, H_i) ppm. **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (150 MHz; CD₂Cl₂): δ_C 154.6, 139.1, 138.5, 138.4, 137.9, 135.0, 134.7, 128.2, 118.3, 115.0, 114.8, 84.5, 82.5, 55.9 ppm. **Acc-MS(ASAP⁺):** *m/z* 569.9558 [M+H]⁺ calcd. for C₂₀H₁₈N₃OI₂ *m/z* 569.9539 (|Δ*m/z*| = 1.9 ppm).*

4-iodo-N'-(4-iodophenyl)-N''-(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)benzimidohydrazide. **Yield:** 4.74 g (73%). **¹H NMR** (600 MHz; CD₂Cl₂): δ_H 7.88 (s, 1H, H_f), 7.72 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.5 Hz, 2H, H_a), 7.53-7.51 (m, 4H, H_d + H_h), 7.45 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.5 Hz, 2H, H_b), 7.18 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.4 Hz, 2H, H_g), 6.49 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.7 Hz, 2H, H_c), 5.68 (s, 1H, H_e) ppm. **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (150 MHz; CD₂Cl₂): δ_C 147.2, 141.0, 138.2, 137.6, 137.1, 133.7, 128.2, 126.4, 125.5, 124.0, 121.6 (d, ¹J_{CF} = 32.5 Hz), 118.1, 112.7, 95.2 ppm. **¹⁹F NMR** (79 MHz; CDCl₃): δ_C -61.36 ppm. **Acc-MS(ASAP⁺):** *m/z* 606.9223 [M]⁺ calcd. for C₂₀H₁₄N₃F₃I₂ *m/z* 606.9229 (|Δ*m/z*| = 1.0 ppm). **Anal. Calc.** for C₂₀H₁₄F₃I₂N₃: C, 39.56; H, 2.32; N, 6.92 %. **Found:** C, 39.56; H, 2.27; N, 3.86 %.

* Compound too unstable for elemental analysis.

4-iodo-N'-(4-iodophenyl)-N''-(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)benzimidohydrazide. **Yield:** 3.61 g (58%). **¹H NMR** (600 MHz; DMSO-d₆): δ_H 10.32 (s, 1H, H_f), 8.56 (s, 1H, H_e), 8.08 (d, ³J_{HH} = 9.5 Hz, 2H, H_h), 7.73 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.5 Hz, 2H, H_d), 7.43 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.7 Hz, 2H, H_a), 7.33 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.5 Hz, 2H, H_c), 7.20 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.8 Hz, 2H, H_g), 6.42 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.7 Hz, 2H, H_b) ppm. **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (150 MHz; DMSO-d₆): δ_C 151.2, 142.4, 141.1, 138.5, 137.7, 133.8, 129.8, 126.4, 120.0, 112.2, 96.4, 82.8 ppm. **Acc-MS**(ASAP⁺): *m/z* 584.9285 [M+H]⁺ calcd. for C₁₉H₁₅N₄O₂¹²⁷I₂ *m/z* 584.9277 (|Δ*m/z*| = 1.4 ppm). **Anal. Calc.** for C₁₉H₁₄I₂N₄O₂: C, 39.07; H, 2.42; N, 9.59 %. **Found:** C, 39.01; H, 2.32; N, 9.59 %.

Diarylbenzimidohydrazide for *meta* isomer general procedure

(4-iodophenyl)hydrazine hydrochloride (1 eq) was slowly added to a solution containing the respective benzimidoyl chloride (1 eq) and anhydrous triethylamine (2 eq) in anhydrous dichloromethane (30 mL) at 0°C. The solution was allowed to warm to room temperature over a period of 16 hours. The solution was washed with 0.1 M HCl, collecting the organic layer, which was dried over MgSO₄ and filtered. Hexane was added to the filtrate until a 3:1 DCM:Hexane solution was achieved. The solution was then passed through a 10 cm long silica plug under pressure, the pale-yellow band was collected and the solvent removed. Hexane was added to the residue and sonicated, forming a pale-yellow precipitate, which was collected by filtration and dried under vacuum. Note: Once isolated, diarylbenzimidohydrazide was unstable in solution after 1 hour, and would slowly decay in the solid-state unless the sample was maintained in a dry, inert atmosphere.

4-iodo-N'-(4-iodophenyl)-N''-phenylbenzimidohydrazide. **Yield:** 6.17 g (78%). **¹H NMR** (600 MHz; DMSO-d₆): δ_H 9.42 (s, 1H, H_g), 8.05 (s, 1H, H_f), 7.66 (d, ³J_{HH} = 7.9 Hz, 2H, H_e), 7.45 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.2 Hz, 2H, H_i), 7.31 (d, ³J_{HH} = 7.9 Hz, 2H, H_d), 7.09 (t, ³J_{HH} = 7.6 Hz, 2H, H_b), 6.96 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.3 Hz, 2H, H_h), 6.71 (t, ³J_{HH} = 7.3 Hz, 1H, H_a), 6.55 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.0 Hz, 2H, H_c) ppm. **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (150 MHz; DMSO-d₆): δ_C 145.8, 143.1, 137.7, 137.4, 134.9, 129.2, 119.8, 117.0, 115.6, 95.0, 80.4 ppm. **Acc-MS(ASAP⁺):** *m/z* 539.9427 [M+H]⁺ calcd. for C₁₉H₁₆I₂N₃ *m/z* 539.9434 (|Δ*m/z*| = 1.3 ppm). **Anal. Calc.** for C₁₉H₁₅I₂N₃: C, 42.33; H, 2.80; N, 7.79 %. **Found:** C, 42.17; H, 2.78; N, 7.74 %.

4-iodo-N'-(4-iodophenyl)-N''-(4-methoxyphenyl)benzimidohydrazide. **Yield:** 1.45 g (19%). **¹H NMR** (600 MHz; CD₂Cl₂): δ_H 7.68 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.6 Hz, 2H, H_b), 7.53-7.50 (m, 3H, H_f+H_g), 7.41 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.5 Hz, 2H, H_a), 6.88 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.8 Hz, 2H, H_h), 6.77 (d, ³J_{HH} = 9.0 Hz, 2H, H_c), 6.66 (d, ³J_{HH} = 8.9 Hz, 2H, H_d), 5.68 (s, 1H, H_e), 3.73 (s, 3H, H_i) ppm. **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (150 MHz; CD₂Cl₂): δ_C 154.7, 145.0, 139.0, 137.7, 134.3, 134.2, 128.5, 118.4, 115.3, 114.6, 94.6, 81.0, 55.4 ppm. **MS(ASAP⁺):** *m/z* 583.9 [M]⁺.[†] **Anal. Calc.** for C₂₀H₁₇I₂N₃O: C, 42.20; H, 3.01; N, 7.38 %. **Found:** C, 42.32; H, 2.90; N, 7.45 %.

Diiodo-Blatter radical general procedure

1,8-Diazabicycloundec-7-ene (DBU) (0.1 eq) was added to a solution containing the respective diarylylbenzimidohydrazide (1.0 eq) and 10% Pd/C (1.6 mol %) in DCM (30 mL). The solution was stirred in an open flask for 16 hours before filtration, the solvent was then removed from the filtrate under vacuo, leaving a red residue. Purification was achieved by recrystallisation in EtOAc twice, forming dark red crystals that were

[†] Compound was too unstable to obtain a HR-MS spectrum

collected by filtration.

H-1-Radical. **Yield:** 536 mg (54%). **Acc-MS(ASAP⁺):** m/z 535.9121 [M+H]⁺ calcd. for C₁₉H₁₂¹²⁷I₂N₃ m/z 535.9144 ($|\Delta m/z| = 4.3$ ppm). **Anal. Calc.** for C₁₉H₁₂I₂N₃: C, 42.57; H, 2.26; N, 7.84 %. **Found:** C, 42.35; H, 2.20; N, 7.78 %.

OMe-1-Radical. **Yield:** 149 mg (15%). **Acc-MS(ASAP⁺):** m/z 565.9211 [M+H]⁺ calcd. for C₂₀H₁₄¹²⁷I₂N₃O m/z 565.9226 ($|\Delta m/z| = 2.7$ ppm). **Anal. Calc.** for C₂₀H₁₄I₂N₃O: C, 42.43; H, 2.49; N, 7.42 %. **Found:** C, 42.36; H, 2.60; N, 7.15 %.

CF₃-1-Radical. **Yield** 0.52 g (53%). **Acc-MS(ASAP⁺):** m/z 604.9078 [M+H]⁺ calcd. for C₂₀H₁₃I₂N₃ m/z 604.9073 ($|\Delta m/z| = 0.8$ ppm). **Anal. Calc.** for C₂₀H₁₁F₃I₂N₃: C, 39.76; H, 1.84; N, 6.96 %. **Found:** C, 39.77; H, 1.89; N, 6.94 %.

NO₂-1-Radical. **Yield:** 548 mg (55%). **MS(ASAP⁺):** m/z 581.904 [M+H]⁺, **Acc-MS(ASAP⁺):** m/z 581.9042 [M+H]⁺ calcd. for C₁₉H₁₂¹²⁷I₂N₄O₂ m/z 581.9050 ($|\Delta m/z| = 1.4$ ppm). **Anal. Calc.** for C₁₉H₁₁I₂N₄O₂·½C₄H₈O₂: C, 40.35; H, 2.42; N, 8.96 %. **Found:** C, 40.20; H, 2.30; N, 9.03 %.

H-2-Radical. **Yield:** 477 mg (48%). **Acc-MS(ASAP⁺):** m/z 535.9106 [M+H]⁺ calcd. for C₁₉H₁₂¹²⁷I₂N₃ m/z 535.9121 ($|\Delta m/z| = 2.8$ ppm). **Anal. Calc.** for C₁₉H₁₂I₂N₃: C, 42.57; H, 2.26; N, 7.84 %. **Found:** C, 42.40; H, 2.23; N, 7.70 %.

MeO-2-Radical. **Yield:** 99 mg (10%). **Acc-MS(ASAP⁺):** m/z 566.9290 $[M+H]^+$ calcd. for $C_{20}H_{15}^{127}I_2N_3O$ m/z 566.9305 ($|\Delta m/z| = 2.6$ ppm). **Anal. Calc.** for $C_{20}H_{14}I_2N_3O$: C, 42.43; H, 2.49; N, 7.42 %. **Found:** C, 42.50; H, 2.47; N, 7.59 %.

Thioacetate-Blatter radical general procedure

A solution of the diiodo-Blatter radical (1 eq) in dry toluene (50 mL) was degassed by bubbling Ar through it for 30 minutes in a Schlenk flask. CuI (0.1 eq), KSAc (10 eq) and 1,10-phenanthroline (0.08 eq) were added while keeping the flask in a gentle stream of dry argon, and the resulting suspension was stirred for 24 h at 100 °C, after which the colour changed to a deep brown. Upon cooling, H₂O (50 mL) was added, and the organic layer was separated. The aqueous layer was extracted using DCM (2 × 25 mL), and the combined organics were washed with brine and dried over MgSO₄. The solvent was removed under vacuo. The residue was dissolved in EtOAc and filtered. The filtrate was collected and the solvent removed under vacuo. The residue was then purified, first through silica chromatography eluted by a gradient from neat DCM to EtOAc:DCM (1:9), and the fraction containing the highest ratio of the product was finally purified using normal phase HPLC, eluted by a solvent gradient from neat DCM to EtOAc.

1.Yield: 380 mg (23%). **Acc-MS(ASAP⁺):** m/z 501.0786 $[M+H]^+$ calcd. for $C_{24}H_{18}F_3N_3O_2S_2$ m/z 501.0793 ($|\Delta m/z| = 1.4$ ppm). **Anal. Calc.** for $C_{24}H_{17}F_3N_3O_2S_2$: C, 57.59 H, 3.42; N, 8.40 %. **Found:** C, 57.75; H, 3.88; N, 8.26 %.

1a Yield: 443 mg (27%). **Acc-MS(ASAP⁺):** m/z 478.0770 $[M+H]^+$ calcd. for $C_{23}H_{18}N_4O_4S_2$ m/z 478.0769 ($|\Delta m/z| = 0.2$ ppm). **Anal. Calc.** for $C_{23}H_{17}N_4O_4S_2$: C, 57.85; H, 3.59; N, 11.73 %. **Found:** C, 57.61; H, 3.70; N, 11.80 %.

2. Yield: 290 mg (18%). **Acc-MS(ASAP⁺):** m/z 501.0809 $[M+H]^+$ calcd. for $C_{24}H_{18}F_3N_3O_2S_2$ m/z 501.0793 ($|\Delta m/z| = 3.2$ ppm). **Anal. Calc.** for $C_{24}H_{17}F_3N_3O_2S_2$: C, 57.59 H, 3.42; N, 8.40 %. **Found:** C, 57.64; H, 3.58; N, 8.19 %.

N-benzyl-4-iodo-*N'*-(4-iodophenyl)benzimidamide. Phenylmethanamine (0.92 g, 8.58 mmol) was slowly added to a solution containing the respective benzimidoyl chloride (4.00 g, 8.58 mmol) and anhydrous triethylamine (1.30 mL, 0.91 g, 9.00 mmol) in anhydrous dichloromethane (30mL) at 0 °C. The solution was allowed to warm to room temperature over a period of 16 hours. The solution was washed with 0.1 M HCl, collecting the organic layer, which was dried over $MgSO_4$ and filtered. Hexane was added to the filtrate until a 3:1 DCM:Hexane solution was achieved. The solution was then passed through a 10 cm long silica plug under pressure, the pale-yellow band was collected and the solvent removed. Hexane was added to the residue and sonicated, forming a pale-yellow precipitate, which was collected by filtration and dried under vacuum. **Yield:** 3.17 g (69%). **¹H NMR** (600 MHz; CD_2Cl_2): δ_H 7.63 (d, $^3J_{HH} = 7.9$ Hz, 2H, H_d), 7.43 (d, $^3J_{HH} = 6.5$ Hz, 2H, H_a), 7.39-7.36 (m, 4H, H_g+H_h), 7.30 (t, $^3J_{HH} = 7.4$ Hz, 2H, H_i), 6.99 (d, $^3J_{HH} = 7.9$ Hz, 2H, H_c), 6.40 (d, $^3J_{HH} = 8.5$ Hz, 2H, H_b), 5.00 (br, 1H, H_e), 4.65 (br, 2H, H_f) ppm. **¹³C{¹H} NMR** (150 MHz; CD_2Cl_2): δ_C 156.2, 150.2, 150.6, 138.8, 137.5, 137.3, 134.0, 130.1, 128.5, 127.8, 127.3, 125.1, 95.5, 84.2, 45.7 ppm. **Acc-MS(ASAP⁺):** m/z 538.9469 $[M+H]^+$ calcd. for $C_{20}H_{17}I_2N_2$ m/z 538.9481 ($|\Delta m/z| = 2.2$ ppm). **Anal. Calc.** for $C_{20}H_{16}I_2N_2$: C, 44.64; H, 3.00; N, 5.21 %. **Found:** C, 44.31; H, 3.99; N, 5.13 %.

6-iodo-2-(4-iodophenyl)-4-phenylquinazoline. A mixture of iodine (2.25 g, 8.92 mmol) and KI (1.472 g, 8.92 mmol) in DMSO (10 mL) was stirred for 10 mins before the addition of *N*-benzyl-4-iodo-*N'*-(4-

iodophenyl)benzimidamide (2.00 g, 3.71 mmol), followed by the addition of K_2CO_3 (1.279 g, 9.27 mmol). The reaction was heated to 100°C under air for 16 hours, before it was poured into MeOH (100 mL), forming a precipitate, which was collected by filtration. Purification was achieved using silica chromatography eluted by neat DCM, giving a white powder. **Yield:** 1.00 g (51%). **1H NMR** (600 MHz; DMSO- d_6): δ_H 8.38-8.36 (m, 3H, H_a+H_e), 8.32 (d, $^3J_{HH} = 8.7$ Hz, $^3J_{HH} = 1.9$ Hz, 1H, H_b), 7.97 (d, $^3J_{HH} = 8.2$ Hz 2H, H_d), 7.94 (d, $^3J_{HH} = 8.7$ Hz 1H, H_c), 7.90-7.87 (m, 2H, H_f), 7.70-7.69 (m, 3H, H_g+H_h) ppm. **$^{13}C\{^1H\}$ NMR** (150 MHz; CD_2Cl_2): δ_C 167.5, 159.1, 150.5, 143.2, 138.1, 137.1, 136.8, 135.5, 131.0, 130.8, 130.5, 130.3, 129.2, 123.2, 99.3, 94.6 ppm. **Acc-MS(ASAP⁺):** m/z 534.9151 $[M+H]^+$ calcd. for $C_{20}H_{12}^{127}I_2N_2$ m/z 534.9166 ($|\Delta m/z| = 3.2$ ppm). **Anal. Calc.** for $C_{20}H_{12}I_2N_2$: C, 44.97 H, 2.26; N, 5.24 %. **Found:** C, 45.15; H, 2.25; N, 5.23 %.

3. A solution of 6-iodo-2-(4-iodophenyl)-4-phenylquinazoline (2.00 g, 3.74 mmol) in dry toluene (50 mL) was degassed by bubbling Ar through it for 30 minutes in a Schlenk flask. CuI (70 mg, 0.37 mmol), KSAc (4.22 g, 37.4 mmol) and 1,10-phenanthroline (54 mg, 0.3 mmol) were added while keeping the flask in a gentle stream of dry argon, and the resulting suspension was stirred for 24 hrs at 100 °C, after which the colour changed to deep brown. Upon cooling, H_2O (50 mL) was added, and the organic layer was separated. The aqueous layer was extracted with DCM (2×25 mL), the combined organics were washed with brine and dried over $MgSO_4$, and the solvent was removed under vacuo. The residue was dissolved in EtOAc and filtered, the filtrate was collected, and the solvent removed under vacuo. The residue was then purified, first through silica chromatography eluted by a gradient from neat DCM to EtOAc:DCM (1:9), and the fraction containing the >75% product was collected. The remaining fractions were then collected and the reaction repeated. This procedure was repeated 10 times, and the fractions containing high product concentrations were combined and purified using silica chromatography eluted by a solvent gradient from neat DCM to EtOAc:DCM (1:9), giving a white solid. **Yield:** 15 mg (0.9 %). **1H NMR** (600 MHz; CD_2Cl_2): δ_H 8.76 (d, $^3J_{HH} = 8.2$ Hz, 2H, H_d), 8.22 (d, $^4J_{HH} = 1.9$ Hz, 1H, H_a), 8.17 (d, $^3J_{HH} = 8.7$ Hz, 1H, c), 7.91-7.88 (m, 3H, H_f+H_b), 7.64-7.63 (m, 3H, H_g+H_h), 7.60 (d, $^3J_{HH} = 8.3$ Hz, 2H, H_e), 2.46 (m, 6H, H_i+H_j) ppm. **Acc-MS(ASAP⁺):** m/z 431.0870 $[M+H]^+$ calcd. for $C_{24}H_{19}N_2O_2S_2$ m/z 431.0888 ($|\Delta m/z| = 4.2$ ppm).

[‡] Sample too insoluble for ^{13}C NMR.

2. NMR data

Figure S8. ^1H NMR spectrum of 4-iodo- N' -(4-iodophenyl)- N'' -phenylbenzimidohydrazide recorded in CD_2Cl_2 .

Figure S9. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of 4-iodo- N' -(4-iodophenyl)- N'' -phenylbenzimidohydrazide recorded in CD_2Cl_2 .

Figure S10. ^1H NMR spectrum of 4-iodo- N' -(4-iodophenyl)- N'' -(4-methoxyphenyl)benzimidohydrazide recorded in CD_2Cl_2 , * indicates decomposition product.

Figure S11. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of 4-iodo- N' -(4-iodophenyl)- N'' -(4-methoxyphenyl)benzimidohydrazide recorded in CD_2Cl_2 .

Figure S12. ^1H NMR spectrum of 4-iodo- N' -(4-iodophenyl)- N'' -(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)benzimidohydrazide recorded in CD_2Cl_2 .

Figure S13. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of 4-iodo- N' -(4-iodophenyl)- N'' -(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)benzimidohydrazide recorded in CD_2Cl_2 .

Figure S14. ^{19}F NMR spectrum of 4-iodo- N' -(4-iodophenyl)- N'' -(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)benzimidohydrazide recorded in CDCl_3 .

Figure S15. ^1H NMR spectrum of 4-iodo- N' -(4-iodophenyl)- N'' -(4-nitrophenyl)benzimidohydrazide recorded in DMSO-d_6 , * indicates decomposition product.

Figure S16. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of 4-iodo- N' -(4-iodophenyl)- N'' -(4-nitrophenyl)benzimidohydrazide recorded in DMSO-d_6 , * indicates decomposition product.

Figure S17. ^1H NMR spectrum of 4-iodo- N' -(4-iodophenyl)- N'' -phenylbenzimidohydrazide recorded in CD_2Cl_2 .

Figure S18. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of 4-iodo- N' -(4-iodophenyl)- N'' -phenylbenzimidohydrazide recorded in CD_2Cl_2 .

Figure S19. ^1H NMR spectrum of 4-iodo- N' -(4-iodophenyl)- N'' -(4-methoxyphenyl)benzimidohydrazide recorded in CD_2Cl_2 .

Figure S20. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of 4-iodo- N' -(4-iodophenyl)- N'' -(4-methoxyphenyl)benzimidohydrazide recorded in CD_2Cl_2 .

Figure S21. ^1H NMR spectrum of N -benzyl-4-iodo- N' -(4-iodophenyl)benzimidamide recorded in DMSO-d_6 .

Figure S22. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of *N*-benzyl-4-iodo-*N'*-(4-iodophenyl)benzimidamide recorded in DMSO-d_6 .

Figure S23. ^1H NMR spectrum of 6-iodo-2-(4-iodophenyl)-4-phenylquinazoline recorded in DMSO-d_6 .

Figure S24. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of 6-iodo-2-(4-iodophenyl)-4-phenylquinazoline recorded in DMSO-d_6 .

Figure S25. ^1H NMR spectrum of *S*-(4-(6-(acetylthio)-4-phenylquinazolin-2-yl)phenyl) ethanethioate recorded in CD_2Cl_2 .

3. HPLC Chromatograms

HPLC was performed using an Interchimic PuriFlash prep HPLC using Puriflash 12 g, HC Spherical Silica, 15 μm , Flash LL Columns eluted using HPLC quality solvents from standard suppliers, running at 28 mL/min.

Figure S26. HPLC chromatogram for compound 1, where solvent A (green) = DCM and solvent B (blue) = ethylacetate.

Figure S27. HPLC chromatogram for compound 1a, where solvent A (green) = DCM and solvent B (blue) = ethylacetate.

Figure S28. HPLC chromatogram for compound 2, where solvent A (green) = DCM and solvent B (blue) = ethylacetate.

4. Photophysical Measurements

UV-Visible absorption spectra were recorded at room-temperature using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer Evolution 220 from Thermo Scientific in quartz cuvettes with path length $l = 1$ cm. The HOMO-LUMO gap of **3** is ca. 1 eV higher than any of the other compounds

Figure S29. UV-Visible absorption spectra for compounds **1**, **1a**, **2** and **3** recorded in DCM.

5. EPR spectroscopy

Samples for EPR measurements were prepared by solvating the Blatter radicals in DCM with the final concentration of radicals of ca. 0.5 mM. All EPR spectra were measured at room temperature using an X-band Bruker EMX spectrometer. The following conditions were used: microwave frequency of 9.50 GHz; microwave power of 2 mW; modulation frequency of 100 kHz; modulation amplitude of 1.0 G. The high stability of the radicals in DCM was confirmed by repeating the measurements after several hours with no noticeable changes in the spectra. EPR spectra were simulated using EasySpin simulation software assuming the fast motional regime¹⁰. g -values and hyperfine coupling constants were obtained from the fitting of experimental EPR spectra. Hyperfine splitting contributions from the nitrogen of the NO₂ group in **1a** were negligible. Spin densities on the nitrogen atoms in the benzotriazinyl ring were estimated using McConnell's equation for the spin density distribution around the benzotriazinyl ring, namely, $A_N = Q_N \rho_N$ ¹¹, where ρ_N and A_N represent the spin density and associated value of the isotropic component of hyperfine coupling tensor, respectively. The values of Q_N constants have been taken from the literature^{11,12}. Spin densities on carbon atoms of CF₃ groups in **1** and **2** radical molecules were estimated using similar McConnell's equation, namely $A_F = Q_F \rho_C$ with the previously reported Q -values of +38.4 Gauss for a CF₃ group attached to a phenyl ring¹³.

Comparisons between experimental and simulated EPR spectra of radical molecules **1**, **1a** and **2** are shown in Figures S30, S31 and S32, respectively. The EPR spectrum of **1a** (Figure S31) in which the CF₃ group is absent shows the characteristic seven line splitting pattern due to the coupling of the unpaired electron to the three slightly non-equivalent ¹⁴N nuclei. The EPR spectrum of radical molecule **2** exhibits eleven lines (Figure S32) due to additional coupling of the unpaired electron to the three equivalent F nuclei of the CF₃ group. In the molecule **1** this splitting is less pronounced due to a lower spin density on CF₃ resulting in only broadening of seven EPR lines (Figure S30).

Figure S30 Comparison between experimental (black) and simulated (red) EPR spectra of the radical molecule **1** in DCM at 295 K. The fitted magnetic parameters are provided in Table S1.

Figure S31 Comparison between experimental (black) and simulated (red) EPR spectra of the radical molecule **1a** in DCM at 295 K. The fitted magnetic parameters are provided in Table S1.

Figure S32 Comparison between experimental (black) and simulated (red) EPR spectra of the radical molecule **2** in DCM at 295 K. The fitted magnetic parameters are provided in Table S1.

Table S1. Magnetic parameters obtained from the fitting of EPR spectra.

Radical	g-value	A(N1)/Gauss	A(N2)/Gauss	A(N3)/Gauss	A(F)/Gauss 3 equivalent F atoms
1	2.0048	7.15	5.01	4.66	1.36
1a	2.0041	6.76	5.05	4.57	n/a
2	2.0054	7.57	5.18	4.81	3.10

Table S2. Estimated spin densities on the N atoms and C atom of CF₃ group from their hyperfine coupling constants.

Radical	N1	N2	N3	C of CF ₃
1	0.286	0.236	0.220	0.035
1a	0.270	0.238	0.215	n/a
2	0.302	0.244	0.227	0.081

6. STM Experiments

a. Sample preparation and junction formation: All compounds were deposited onto Au(111) samples using the drop casting technique. Au samples were annealed at approximately 900 K for 1-2 minutes, allowed to cool down to room temperature and then introduced into a 1 mM dichloromethane (DCM) solution of the corresponding molecule. After 40 minutes samples were dried off with nitrogen gas to eliminate possible molecular clusters on the surface. Mechanically cut Au wires (0.25 mm diameter, 99.99% purity, Goodfellow) were used as STM tips. A bias voltage was applied to the sample, using $V_{bias} = 100$ mV for **2** and **3**, and $V_{bias} = 200$ mV for **1**, and a series resistor of 12 M Ω . The tunnelling current was amplified using a double-stage, home-made, linear current-voltage (I-V)-converter with an overall gain of 2.5×10^{10} V/A (5×10^8 V/A in the first stage and multiplied by a factor of 50 in the second one).

To form the molecular junctions, the STM tip was repeatedly indented into the Au sample and then retracted while the current was recorded. When having enough molecules on the surface, there is the possibility to create a molecular junction between the electrodes just after the monoatomic Au-Au contact breaks. This whole process is called an *IZ* curve (tunnelling current I vs tip displacement Z) and the statistical analysis of the electrical conductance G of the molecular junctions (where $G = I/V_{bias}$) is performed collecting thousands of *IZ* curves. In particular, we build 1D conductance histograms, considering only the conductance values, as well as 2D conductance histograms, showing the conductance vs the tip displacement for all the curves. In the case of the 2D histograms, the zero tip-sample displacement is set for each *IZ* curve on the monoatomic Au-Au breakage.

b. Conductance experiments and clustering technique: The clustering analysis applied was based on the k-means algorithm supported by Matlab. To transform the *IZ* curves into valid inputs for the algorithm, we assign a Lorentzian distribution to each conductance point and then we add up all of them. The number of clusters was initially chosen to be 2 and was then successively increased until the complete conductance distribution was properly fitted, without major overlapping between the conductance clusters¹⁴. Applying this analysis, we find that for the three compounds investigated the complete conductance histograms are properly fitted using three different clusters for each of them, named *low-plateau* (LP), *middle-plateau* (MP) and *high-plateau* (HP) clusters. Figure S33 shows all 1D conductance histograms for all the compounds (the complete histogram and the histogram corresponding to each cluster, together with the percentage of curves in each of them) and Figure S34 shows the 2D histograms for each conductance cluster.

Figure S33. 1D conductance histograms for all molecules. a-c. 1D conductance histograms for compounds 1-3, respectively. Black lines show the complete histogram for each molecule, while colored lines are conductance histograms obtained after the clustering technique is applied. Each molecule presents three clusters, named *low-plateau* (LP) (dashed line), *middle-plateau* (MP) (solid line) and *high-plateau* (HP) (dashed-point line). The percentage of curves included in each cluster is given in the legend of each panel.

Considering these 2D histograms, the mean plateau length for the junctions in each cluster has been also investigated. First, we consider the 1D conductance histogram of each cluster and, fitting the conductance peak with a Gaussian distribution, the corresponding mean conductance value G_m and the standard deviation σ_G are obtained. Then, we find, for each individual curve, the tip displacement value for $G = G_m + \sigma_G$ and $G = G_m - \sigma_G$, get the distance between them and collect all the values in a 1D histogram with the individual lengths. Finally, a Gaussian distribution is fitted to the histogram. The mean plateau lengths considered for each cluster (given in Figure S34) are the length values where the Gaussian distributions decay to 90% of the mean value¹⁵.

Considering the analysis of the electrical conductance of the three compounds, the origin of the three different clusters for each of them can be addressed, since they correspond to statistically significant junction configurations. Low *et al.*¹⁶ showed that Blatter radical structures typically present two kind of conductance junctions, corresponding to monomer (single molecule) and dimer (two molecules in series) configurations. Their reported conductance values and plateau lengths are similar to those found in this work for the MP and LP clusters, respectively, suggesting that in our experiments the MP cluster might correspond to a monomer configuration while the LP cluster might be a consequence of a dimer configuration.

c. Seebeck coefficient experiments: To perform Seebeck coefficient measurements a home-built STM was used, capable of measuring simultaneously the conductance (G) and the thermovoltage (V_{th}) of the molecular junctions formed. The tip was heated using a 1 K Ω surface resistor, creating a temperature difference (ΔT) between the tip and the sample, with the tip at $T_h > T_{ambient}$ and the sample at $T_c = T_{ambient}$. This temperature difference not only generates a V_{th} in the molecular junction but also in the copper lead that connects the tip to the rest of the setup. Considering all these factors the thermoelectric equation of the circuit can be expressed as:

$$I = G(V_{bias} + V_{th}) = G(V_{bias} + S\Delta T - S_{lead}\Delta T), \quad (2)$$

where S and S_{lead} are the Seebeck coefficients of the molecule and the copper lead, respectively. Figure S35a

shows a scheme of the equivalent electrical-thermal circuit of the STM.

Figure S34. 2D conductance histograms. **a-c.** 2D histograms of each cluster identified for compound **1**, named *low-plateau* (LP), *middle-plateau* (MP) and *high-plateau* (HP) clusters, respectively, **d-f.** The same as a-c but for compound **2**, and **g-i**, the same as a-c but for compound **3**. The mean plateau length for the junctions in each cluster is given in each panel as l_m .

While forming the molecular junctions, small IV curves of ± 10 mV are acquired to perform the thermoelectric characterization. An example of the tip displacement Z and the bias voltage V_{bias} signals applied in this case are shown in Figure 35b-c, respectively. The tip displacement is momentarily stopped during the junction formation and the small IV curves are measured. Applying equation (2), V_{th} and G are simultaneously obtained from the zero-current crossing point and the slope of the IV curves, respectively, and the Seebeck coefficient is then given by $S = -V_{th}/\Delta T$.

Figure S35. Seebeck coefficient experiments **a.** Scheme of the electrical-thermal circuit of the STM, where V_{bias} is the bias voltage applied; S and S_{lead} are the Seebeck coefficients of the molecule and the copper lead, respectively; G is the conductance of the molecular junction, and ΔT is the temperature difference between the tip (at $T_h > T_c$) and the sample ($T_c = T_{\text{ambient}}$), and **b-c.** Tip displacement Z and V_{bias} signals, respectively, during a thermovoltage measurement. While the molecular junction is formed, the tip displacement is momentarily stopped and the V_{bias} is ramped between ± 10 mV.

Figure S36. 1D Seebeck coefficient histograms. Seebeck coefficient histograms (solid lines) and Gaussian fits (dashed lines) for molecules **1-3**. The standard deviation of each Gaussian distribution (σ) is given as an inset. The blue curve corresponds to compound **1**; the red curve, to **2**, and the yellow curve, to **3**.

For consistency, the clustering technique discussed above (Section 6b) was also applied to the IZ curves measured for the thermoelectric characterization, considering only the junctions included in the *middle-plateau* (MP) cluster for the analysis. Figure S36 shows the 1D histograms of all the Seebeck coefficient data points included in these clusters ($S = -V_{th}/\Delta T$ applied to each individual V_{th} value). It can be observed in these histograms, where Gaussian fits have been applied to each of them, that compound **2** has not only the largest most probable S , as discussed in the main text, but also the largest standard deviation. This suggests that the transmission function of **2** around the Fermi energy might be steeper than for compounds **1** and **3**, in good agreement with the theoretical calculations.

d. Spectroscopy experiments: Spectroscopy measurements were performed for the three molecules by acquiring large IV curves (± 1 V). During the tip displacement the V_{bias} was fixed at 100 mV and the IV curves were taken during the complete IZ range. The curves were then transformed to $\log G(G_0)$ vs V curves (i.e. GV curves) to facilitate comparison and two different filters were applied to select the GV curves to be considered in the statistical analysis. The first filter was a manual selection of IZ curves, including only those with a clear molecular plateau, and the second one was a selection of the GV curves with a low-voltage slope between -4.0 and -5.0, in logarithmic scale, to avoid the saturation of the current signal and the electrical noise level. The selected GV curves are shown in Figure S37, where the low-bias-voltage values were gently smoothed to avoid the divergence of the signal at zero bias voltage. The average curve for each compound is also plotted. Additionally, individual examples of the spectroscopy experiments can be found in Figure S38.

Figure S37. 2D Conductance-voltage (GV) histograms of all compounds: 1 (a), 2 (b) and 3 (c). All the selected GV curves and the average curve for each compound (in black) are shown.

Figure S38. Examples of individual spectroscopy measurements. **a.** Individual GZ curve for compound 1 (in blue). Black circles highlight the points where GV curves are acquired, **d.** Corresponding GV curves measured at the molecular plateau shown in panel **a** and at the positions marked by the black circles. **b,e.** The same as panels **a** and **d**, but for compound 2 (in red). **c,f.** The same as panels **a** and **d**, but for compound 3 (in yellow).

e. 1a measurements.

To complete the study of the compounds, G and S were measured for compound **1a**, shown in Figure S39. As predicted by theoretical calculations, the Seebeck coefficient of compound **1a** ($8.5 \mu\text{V/K}$) decreases compared to compounds **1** and **2**, while the conductance of the MP cluster ($\log(G/G_0) = -3.8$) remains almost constant.

Figure S39. Conductance and Seebeck coefficient of compound 1a. **a.** 1D conductance histograms for compound **1a**. The black line shows the complete histogram, while colored lines are conductance histograms of the three clusters: *low-plateau* (LP) (dashed line), *middle-plateau* (MP) (solid line) and *high-plateau* (HP) (dashed-point line). The percentage of curves included in each cluster is given in the legend. **b.** Mean thermovoltage ($\overline{V_{th}}$) and standard deviation values (σ_{th}) from Gaussian fits. $\overline{V_{th}}$ and σ_{th} are represented by empty circles and error bars, respectively. The Seebeck coefficient of compound **1a** is the slope of a linear regression to all the individual V_{th} vs ΔT data points, given in the panel.

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